

Vertebrate hemoglobin - a dioxygen transporter or protogasoreceptor?

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Running title: Vertebrate hemoglobin - a dioxygen transporter or protogasoreceptor?

Keywords: oxygen sensing, hemoglobin, oxygen receptor

The major role of hemoglobin in vertebrates is to transport dioxygen and carbon dioxide. Additionally, its heme cofactor-based enzymatic activity generates nitrite oxide during hypoxia, which is a well-accepted gaseous signaling molecule. It is clear that hemoglobin is additionally expressed in cells other than erythrocytes. This raises the question: Does hemoglobin merely transport dioxygen in such cells, or does it perform additional functions? Furthermore, although vertebrate dioxygen sensing mechanisms are largely attributed to the HIF1 α /PHD2 pathway, the identity of dioxygen-sensing gasoreceptors is unknown. Since hemoglobin's enzymatic activity depends on dioxygen binding status, I propose that it as a protogasoreceptor for dioxygen. Additionally, since hemoglobin can interact with and potentially regulate the activity of other proteins with potential signal transducer functions, I also propose that hemoglobin is a dioxygen-sensing gasoreceptor in such instances. Overall, vertebrate hemoglobin is one of the major gasoreceptors that sense dioxygen status and mediate gasocrine signaling.

1 IF THERE IS A GASORECEPTOR FOR NITRIC OXIDE, IS THERE A GASORECEPTOR FOR DIOXYGEN?

Gases are evolutionarily old signaling molecules and major regulators of cellular metabolism (Aono, 2017; Canfield, 2014). Embryo development is one of the crucial timepoints in which gas homeostasis in cells must be tightly regulated to prevent developmental disorders and embryonic lethality (Maltepe et al., 1997; Froehlich-Santino et al., 2014; Pan et al., 2024). It is conceivable that the diffusion of gases may also provide and regulate positional information and tissue scaling during embryogenesis (Čapek & Müller, 2019; Anbalagan, 2024c). For example, in a variety of vertebrate and invertebrate embryos, exposure to an anoxic environment can lead to developmental arrest or suspended animation (Padilla and Roth, 2001; Teodoro and O'Farrell, 2003). Apart from dioxygen (O₂), an environmentally-derived essential gaseous molecule for vertebrates, other gaseous molecules such as nitric oxide, carbon monoxide, hydrogen sulfide, methane, and ethylene are synthesized in developing cells (Carlew et al., 2020; R. Wang, 2002). The molecular machinery that synthesizes these gases is highly conserved throughout evolution. This suggests the potential importance of these molecules for signaling and maintaining cellular homeostasis throughout an animal's life. Nevertheless, knowledge about the precise signaling role of gases during embryo development is currently lacking. Although vertebrate O₂ sensing mechanisms are largely attributed to the HIF1 α /PHD2 pathway, the identity of direct O₂ sensing gasoreceptors, similar to the nitric oxide (NO)-sensing hemoprotein-based gasoreceptors soluble guanylate cyclase and REV-ERB β are still unknown (Anbalagan, 2024c; Dioum et al., 2002; Hammarlund et al., 2020; Horst et al., 2019; Moreno-Domínguez et al., 2020; Pardee et al., 2009).

2 DIOXYGEN-SENSING ONE-COMPONENT SIGNALING SYSTEMS

In terms of the classification of signaling systems in prokaryotes, the NO gasoreceptor soluble guanylate cyclase can be described as an example of one-component signaling system (Ulrich et al., 2005; Wuichet et al., 2010). Similarly, the O₂-sensing gasoreceptors (DosP phosphodiesterase, GCY-35 soluble guanylate cyclase, and HemAc-Lm soluble adenylate cyclase) in *Escherichia coli*, *C. elegans*, and *Leishmania major* also appear to be one-component signaling systems (**Figure 1**). These gasoreceptors contain both the heme-based O₂-binding domain and the signaling domains of diverse activities ranging from enzymes, transcription factors to ion channels (Aono, 2017; Delgado-Nixon et al., 2000; Monson et al., 1992; Anbalagan, 2024a). Thus, although O₂ sensors that appear to function as gasoreceptors have been reported in various other model organisms, it is surprising that,

to date, knowledge of vertebrate O₂ sensing is based solely on O₂-sensors (Hammarlund et al., 2020; López-Barneo et al., 2016; Moreno-Domínguez et al., 2020). Then, a question arises: Does this mean that there are no vertebrate O₂ gasoreceptors or does O₂-sensing occur only via sensors? Are there vertebrate O₂-sensing gasoreceptors that function as either as one- or two-component signaling systems? Androglobin (ADGB) is a promising candidate for a vertebrate O₂ gasoreceptor. It has been reported to bind O₂ and required for sperm development, but it is unclear whether its protease activity by its O₂-binding status (Anbalagan, 2024d; Keppner et al., 2022). Moreover, androglobin can also bind nitric oxide as a five-coordinate complex, it is unclear whether it acts as a gasoreceptor for O₂ or nitric oxide, or both (Reeder et al., 2024).

3 IS HEMOGLOBIN A PROTOGASORECEPTOR & AN EXAMPLE OF PROTO-COMPONENT SIGNALING SYSTEM?

One-component signaling systems are evolutionarily advanced in terms of the number of protein domains (Ulrich et al., 2005). It is likely that simpler proteins with fewer domains perform both the gas-sensing role and signaling roles directly. For candidate O₂-sensing gasoreceptors, globins are the most promising (Vinogradov et al., 2006).

The role of archaeal, bacterial, and yeast protoglobins and flavohemoglobins was proposed to be that of enzymes such as nitrite reductase, nitric oxide dioxygenase, denitrosylase, and alkylhydroperoxide reductase, rather than that of gas transport (Zhu & Riggs, 1992; Bonamore et al., 2003; Corker & Poole, 2003; Freitas et al., 2004; Ascenzi et al., 2014). Similar enzymatic activity has also been reported in plant phytoglobins (Mukhi et al., 2017; Villar et al., 2020). Furthermore, it can also participate in nitric oxide scavenging in various organisms (Angelo et al., 2008).

It has been reported that human hemoglobin too exhibits nitrite reductase activity and generates nitric oxide during hypoxia in a nitric oxide synthase-independent manner (Basu et al., 2007; Dent et al., 2021; Gladwin & Kim-Shapiro, 2008; Helms & Kim-Shapiro, 2013). Whether nitric oxide generated from hemoglobin acts as a signaling molecule *in vivo* in or between organelles or cells is under debate (Dent et al., 2021). But due to the abundance of hemoglobin and possibility of hemoglobin traversing or localized in hypoxic regions, it is challenging to dismiss the potential nitric oxide-based signaling role of hemoglobin. Moreover, if the O₂ binding can competitively inhibit hemoglobin's enzyme activity, isn't the "nitric oxide-based signaling" role of the hemoglobin under hypoxic conditions is also blocked. These arguments warrants us to consider hemoglobin as an O₂-sensing protogasoreceptor and if hemoglobin is an O₂- (or other gas)-sensing proto-component

signaling system (**Figure 2**) (Minning et al., 1999; S. Wang et al., 2017, 2021). Likewise, similar arguments must also be extended to other hemoproteins that exhibits various enzymatic activities. For instance, androglobin and cytoglobin has been demonstrated to exhibit nitrite reductase and nitric oxide dioxygenase activity, respectively (Reeder, 2023; Reeder et al., 2024).

4 DIOXYGEN-SENSING SPLIT-COMPONENT SIGNALING SYSTEMS

But in addition to one-component signaling systems, there are also the examples of two-component signaling systems in which the signal transduction occurs via the phosphorylation of a response regulator (Wuichet et al., 2010). Such multi-component signaling systems has been also reported in microbial gas-sensing mechanisms (Lenz & Friedrich, 1998; Buhrke et al., 2004). The glucokinase regulator GCKR (also known as GKRP, glucokinase regulatory protein) can be potentially considered as a fructose 1-phosphate & fructose 6-phosphate-sensing receptor and glucokinase as one of its signal transducers (Anbalagan, 2025; Beck & Miller, 2013). The fructose-sensing GCKR and glucokinase can be considered as split-component signaling systems.

The presence of splice-component signaling system for sugars, raises the question of the identity of vertebrate O₂-sensing split-component signaling systems. Theoretically, any O₂-binding protein that can physically interact with an enzyme and affect enzyme activity can potentially considered as a split-component signaling system. In such a scenario, major O₂-binding proteins hemoglobin, cytoglobin, neuroglobin, and myoglobin can also be considered as putative O₂-sensing gasoreceptors and their interacting enzymes as potential signal transducers, provided that the O₂-dependent binding status with the enzymes promotes or inhibits the enzyme activity.

5 HEMOGLOBIN AND SLC4A1 IS AN DIOXYGEN-SENSING SPLIT-COMPONENT SIGNALING SYSTEM

If we consider vertebrate hemoglobin as a split-component signaling system, what is the identity of signal transducers in such systems in different cell types including mature erythrocytes? (Ellsworth et al., 2009) Another question to consider is what can be a signal transducer in a split-component signaling systems? Can it only be enzymes or can it be also other classes of proteins such as membranal anion exchangers? If receptors in one-component signaling systems can be both ion channels (e.g., temperature-sensing TRPV ion channels) and enzymes (e.g., NO-sensing soluble guanylate cyclase), why not also consider ion channels or anion exchangers as signal transducers? (Dhaka et al., 2006; Horst et al., 2019) As hemoglobin can bind to SLC4A1 (also known as band 3 anion exchanger,

AE1) in an O₂-binding status-dependent manner and can affect SLC4A1 functions in exchange of bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) for chloride (Cl⁻) ions, erythrocyte properties, survival, and mouse physiology, I propose hemoglobin as an O₂-sensing gasoreceptor and SLC4A1 as one of its signal transducers in a split-component signaling system (**Figure 2**) (Cendali et al., 2024, p. 3; Chu et al., 2016; Jennings, 2021). However, one potential pitfall of this proposal though is the need to distinguish between the role of O₂-sensing and CO₂-interaction at the N-terminal amino groups of globin chains in hemoglobin, which favors the deoxyhemoglobin state (Kilmartin & Rossi-Bernardi, 1971; Perrella et al., 1975).

6 HEMOGLOBIN: A DIOXYGEN TRANSPORTER OR A (PROTO)GASORECEPTOR?

Finally, regarding the argument that the major role of hemoglobin is to transport O₂. This role largely depends on the fact that erythrocytes are passively carried in the blood flow, and not on the chaperone role of hemoglobin for O₂ in cells. Hemoglobin and the nitric oxide gasoreceptor soluble guanylate cyclase both exhibit reversible binding of O₂ and nitric oxide, respectively (Kharitonov et al., 1997; Winger et al., 2007). Relatively mobile cells, such as platelets, neutrophils, and macrophages, also express soluble guanylate cyclase (Ciuman et al., 2006; Makhoul et al., 2018). However, it is well accepted in these cell types that soluble guanylate cyclase is a nitric oxide gasoreceptor and not a nitric oxide transporter. Similarly, hemoglobin is not only expressed in erythrocytes in vertebrates. The expression of hemoglobin subunits has been reported in alveolar epithelial cells, endothelial cells, dopaminergic neurons, glial cells and macrophages, and even in organelles such as mitochondria (Biagioli et al., 2009; Dunaway et al., 2024; Reed et al., 2025; Saha et al., 2014; Shephard et al., 2014). These findings suggest that, similar to soluble guanylate cyclase, hemoglobin is also expressed in various mobile and non-mobile cells in animals. Thus, although it needs to be determined how much of nitric oxide that reaches other nitric oxide gasoreceptors in the cytoplasm, organelles, or neighboring cells when it unbinds from soluble guanylate cyclase, it is difficult to dismiss the possibility that hemoglobin is a protogasoreceptor or gasoreceptor for O₂ (and other gases that can compete with O₂ binding).

7 CONCLUSION

The major role of vertebrate hemoglobin's has been accepted as O₂ and CO₂ transporter. However, based on all the above listed arguments, I propose vertebrate hemoglobin is one of the major gasoreceptors that sense dioxygen status directly and mediate gasocrine signaling (Anbalagan, 2024c). Additionally, as I proposed earlier, hemoglobin is potentially also as a water-sensing aquareceptor and protoaquareceptor (Anbalagan, 2024b). Similar

to hemoglobin, all the other O₂-binding globins and other O₂-binding proteins must be considered as putative gasoreceptors, provided their enzymatic activity or activity of interacting signal transducer activity (e.g., enzymes, ion channels, or anion exchangers) is affected by O₂ binding.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Savani Anbalagan: conceptualization, writing of the original draft, and review and editing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author thank Zofia Szweykowska-Kulinska (Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland) for allowing him to attend her inspiring lectures on molecular evolution. The author also thank Agnieszka Chacinska (Past affiliation: Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw, Regenerative Mechanisms for Health - International Research Agendas Programme and current affiliation: International Institute of Molecular Machines and Mechanisms, Polish Academy of Science, Warsaw, Poland) for suggesting him to attend the 44th FEBS Congress meeting. The author is supported by National Science Centre grants (SONATA-BIS 2020/38/E/NZ3/00090 and SONATA 2021/43/D/NZ3/01798). The author also thanks José López Barneo (University of Seville, Spain) and James Imlay (University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign, Illinois, USA) for e-discussions on oxygen sensing.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

The funding agency and institution S.A. is affiliated with was not involved in the contents of the manuscript. The author used DeepL Write for English-language correction and takes full responsibility for the content of the manuscript.

ETHICS STATEMENT

None of the experiments and procedures on humans and animals is contained in this study.

REFERENCES

- Anbalagan, S. (2024a). Gas-sensing riboreceptors. *RNA Biology*, 21(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15476286.2024.2379607>
- Anbalagan, S. (2024b). [Heme-based aquareceptors]. *Postepy Biochemii*, 70(3), 420–423. https://doi.org/10.18388/pb.2021_551
- Anbalagan, S. (2024c). Heme-based oxygen gasoreceptors. *American Journal of Physiology. Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 326(2), E178–E181. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpendo.00004.2024>
- Anbalagan, S. (2024d). Oxygen is an essential gasotransmitter directly sensed via protein gasoreceptors. *Animal Models and Experimental Medicine*, 7(2), 189–193. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ame2.12400>
- Anbalagan, S. (2025). Sugar-sensing swodkoreceptors and swodkocrine signaling. *Animal Models and Experimental Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ame2.70007>
- Angelo, M., Hausladen, A., Singel, D. J., & Stamler, J. S. (2008). Interactions of NO with hemoglobin: From microbes to man. *Methods in Enzymology*, 436, 131–168. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879\(08\)36008-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879(08)36008-X)
- Aono, S. (2017). *Gas Sensing in Cells*. Royal Society of Chemistry.
- Ascenzi, P., Leboffe, L., Pesce, A., Ciaccio, C., Sbardella, D., Bolognesi, M., & Coletta, M. (2014). Nitrite-reductase and peroxynitrite isomerization activities of Methanosarcina acetivorans protoglobin. *PloS One*, 9(5), e95391. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0095391>
- Basu, S., Grubina, R., Huang, J., Conradie, J., Huang, Z., Jeffers, A., Jiang, A., He, X., Azarov, I., Seibert, R., Mehta, A., Patel, R., King, S. B., Hogg, N., Ghosh, A., Gladwin, M. T., & Kim-Shapiro, D. B. (2007). Catalytic generation of N2O3 by the concerted nitrite reductase and anhydrase activity of hemoglobin. *Nature Chemical Biology*, 3(12), 785–794. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nchembio.2007.46>
- Beck, T., & Miller, B. G. (2013). Structural basis for regulation of human glucokinase by glucokinase regulatory protein. *Biochemistry*, 52(36), 6232–6239. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bi400838t>
- Biagioli, M., Pinto, M., Cesselli, D., Zaninello, M., Lazarevic, D., Roncaglia, P., Simone, R., Vlachouli, C., Plessy, C., Bertin, N., Beltrami, A., Kobayashi, K., Gallo, V., Santoro, C., Ferrer, I., Rivella, S., Beltrami, C. A., Carninci, P., Raviola, E., & Gustincich, S. (2009). Unexpected expression of alpha- and beta-globin in mesencephalic dopaminergic neurons and glial cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 106(36), 15454–15459. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0813216106>
- Bonamore, A., Gentili, P., Ilari, A., Schininà, M. E., & Boffi, A. (2003). Escherichia coli flavohemoglobin is an efficient alkylhydroperoxide reductase. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 278(25), 22272–22277. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M301285200>
- Buhrke, T., Lenz, O., Porthun, A., & Friedrich, B. (2004). The H₂-sensing complex of Ralstonia eutropha: Interaction between a regulatory [NiFe] hydrogenase and a histidine protein kinase. *Molecular Microbiology*, 51(6), 1677–1689. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2958.2003.03933.x>
- Canfield, D. E. (2014). *Oxygen: A Four Billion Year History*. Princeton University Press.
- Čapek, D., & Müller, P. (2019). Positional information and tissue scaling during development and regeneration. *Development (Cambridge, England)*, 146(24), dev177709. <https://doi.org/10.1242/dev.177709>
- Carlew, T. S., Allen, C. J., & Binder, B. M. (2020). Ethylene Receptors in Nonplant Species. *Small Methods*, 4(8), 1900266. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.201900266>
- Cendali, F. I., Grier, A., Lisk, C., Dzieciatkowska, M., Swindle, D., Hay, A. M., Nemkov, T., Irwin, D., Zimring, J., & D'Alessandro, A. (2024). Got Oxygen? The Impact of Band 3 on RBC Function

- during Exercise. *Blood*, *144*(Supplement 1), 3847. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2024-210637>
- Chu, H., McKenna, M. M., Krump, N. A., Zheng, S., Mendelsohn, L., Thein, S. L., Garrett, L. J., Bodine, D. M., & Low, P. S. (2016). Reversible binding of hemoglobin to band 3 constitutes the molecular switch that mediates O₂ regulation of erythrocyte properties. *Blood*, *128*(23), 2708–2716. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2016-01-692079>
- Ciuman, M., Siednienko, J., Czyzyk, R., Witwicka, H., Kołosionek, E., Kobińska, M., & Gorczyca, W. A. (2006). Cyclic GMP-dependent protein kinase and soluble guanylyl cyclase disappear in elicited rat neutrophils. *Biochimica Et Biophysica Acta*, *1760*(11), 1618–1623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2006.09.002>
- Corker, H., & Poole, R. K. (2003). Nitric Oxide Formation by *Escherichia coli*: DEPENDENCE ON NITRITE REDUCTASE, THE NO-SENSING REGULATOR Fnr, AND FLAVOHEMOGLOBIN Hmp*. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, *278*(34), 31584–31592. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M303282200>
- Delgado-Nixon, V. M., Gonzalez, G., & Gilles-Gonzalez, M. A. (2000). Dos, a heme-binding PAS protein from *Escherichia coli*, is a direct oxygen sensor. *Biochemistry*, *39*(10), 2685–2691. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bi991911s>
- Dent, M. R., DeMartino, A. W., Tejero, J., & Gladwin, M. T. (2021). Endogenous Hemoprotein-Dependent Signaling Pathways of Nitric Oxide and Nitrite. *Inorganic Chemistry*, *60*(21), 15918–15940. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.1c01048>
- Dhaka, A., Viswanath, V., & Patapoutian, A. (2006). Trp ion channels and temperature sensation. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*, *29*, 135–161. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.neuro.29.051605.112958>
- Dioum, E. M., Rutter, J., Tuckerman, J. R., Gonzalez, G., Gilles-Gonzalez, M.-A., & McKnight, S. L. (2002). NPAS2: A gas-responsive transcription factor. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, *298*(5602), 2385–2387. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1078456>
- Dunaway, L., Nyshadham, S., Luse, M., Loeb, S., Sveeggen, T., Bagher, P., Goldfarb, A., & Isakson, B. (2024). Endothelial Hemoglobin Alpha Mediates Iron Regulation of Endothelial Nitric Oxide. *Physiology*, *39*(S1), 466. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physiol.2024.39.S1.466>
- Ellsworth, M. L., Ellis, C. G., Goldman, D., Stephenson, A. H., Dietrich, H. H., & Sprague, R. S. (2009). Erythrocytes: Oxygen Sensors and Modulators of Vascular Tone in Regions of Low PO₂. *Physiology (Bethesda, Md.)*, *24*, 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physiol.00038.2008>
- Freitas, T. A. K., Hou, S., Dioum, E. M., Saito, J. A., Newhouse, J., Gonzalez, G., Gilles-Gonzalez, M.-A., & Alam, M. (2004). Ancestral hemoglobins in Archaea. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *101*(17), 6675–6680. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0308657101>
- Froehlich-Santino, W., Tobon, A. L., Cleveland, S., Torres, A., Phillips, J., Cohen, B., Torigoe, T., Miller, J., Fedele, A., Collins, J., Smith, K., Lotspeich, L., Croen, L. A., Ozonoff, S., Lajonchere, C., Grether, J. K., O'Hara, R., & Hallmayer, J. (2014). Prenatal and Perinatal Risk Factors in a Twin Study of Autism Spectrum Disorders. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, *54*, 100–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2014.03.019>
- Gladwin, M. T., & Kim-Shapiro, D. B. (2008). The functional nitrite reductase activity of the heme-globins. *Blood*, *112*(7), 2636–2647. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2008-01-115261>
- Hammarlund, E. U., Flashman, E., Mohlin, S., & Licausi, F. (2020). Oxygen-sensing mechanisms across eukaryotic kingdoms and their roles in complex multicellularity. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, *370*(6515), eaba3512. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba3512>
- Helms, C., & Kim-Shapiro, D. B. (2013). Hemoglobin-mediated nitric oxide signaling. *Free Radical Biology & Medicine*, *0*, 464–472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2013.04.028>
- Horst, B. G., Yokom, A. L., Rosenberg, D. J., Morris, K. L., Hammel, M., Hurley, J. H., & Marletta, M. A. (2019). Allosteric activation of the nitric oxide receptor soluble guanylate cyclase mapped by cryo-electron microscopy. *eLife*, *8*, e50634. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.50634>

- Jennings, M. L. (2021). Cell physiology and molecular mechanism of anion transport by erythrocyte band 3/AE1. *American Journal of Physiology. Cell Physiology*, 321(6), C1028–C1059. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpcell.00275.2021>
- Keppner, A., Correia, M., Santambrogio, S., Koay, T. W., Maric, D., Osterhof, C., Winter, D. V., Clerc, A., Stumpe, M., Chalmel, F., Dewilde, S., Odermatt, A., Kressler, D., Hankeln, T., Wenger, R. H., & Hoogewijs, D. (2022). Androglobin, a chimeric mammalian globin, is required for male fertility. *eLife*, 11, e72374. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.72374>
- Kharitonov, V. G., Russwurm, M., Magde, D., Sharma, V. S., & Koesling, D. (1997). Dissociation of nitric oxide from soluble guanylate cyclase. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 239(1), 284–286. <https://doi.org/10.1006/bbrc.1997.7470>
- Kilmartin, J. V., & Rossi-Bernardi, L. (1971). The binding of carbon dioxide by horse haemoglobin. *The Biochemical Journal*, 124(1), 31–45. <https://doi.org/10.1042/bj1240031>
- Lenz, O., & Friedrich, B. (1998). A novel multicomponent regulatory system mediates H₂ sensing in *Alcaligenes eutrophus*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 95(21), 12474–12479. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.95.21.12474>
- López-Barneo, J., González-Rodríguez, P., Gao, L., Fernández-Agüera, M. C., Pardal, R., & Ortega-Sáenz, P. (2016). Oxygen sensing by the carotid body: Mechanisms and role in adaptation to hypoxia. *American Journal of Physiology-Cell Physiology*, 310(8), C629–C642. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpcell.00265.2015>
- Makhoul, S., Walter, E., Pagel, O., Walter, U., Sickmann, A., Gambaryan, S., Smolenski, A., Zahedi, R. P., & Jurk, K. (2018). Effects of the NO/soluble guanylate cyclase/cGMP system on the functions of human platelets. *Nitric Oxide: Biology and Chemistry*, 76, 71–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.niox.2018.03.008>
- Maltepe, E., Schmidt, J. V., Baunoch, D., Bradfield, C. A., & Simon, M. C. (1997). Abnormal angiogenesis and responses to glucose and oxygen deprivation in mice lacking the protein ARNT. *Nature*, 386(6623), 403–407. <https://doi.org/10.1038/386403a0>
- Minning, D. M., Gow, A. J., Bonaventura, J., Braun, R., Dewhirst, M., Goldberg, D. E., & Stamler, J. S. (1999). Ascaris haemoglobin is a nitric oxide-activated “deoxygenase.” *Nature*, 401(6752), 497–502. <https://doi.org/10.1038/46822>
- Monson, E. K., Weinstein, M., Ditta, G. S., & Helinski, D. R. (1992). The FixL protein of *Rhizobium meliloti* can be separated into a heme-binding oxygen-sensing domain and a functional C-terminal kinase domain. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 89(10), 4280–4284. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.89.10.4280>
- Moreno-Domínguez, A., Ortega-Sáenz, P., Gao, L., Colinas, O., García-Flores, P., Bonilla-Henao, V., Aragonés, J., Hüttemann, M., Grossman, L. I., Weissmann, N., Sommer, N., & López-Barneo, J. (2020). Acute O₂ sensing through HIF2 α -dependent expression of atypical cytochrome oxidase subunits in arterial chemoreceptors. *Science Signaling*, 13(615), eaay9452. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scisignal.aay9452>
- Mukhi, N., Kundu, S., & Kaur, J. (2017). NO dioxygenase- and peroxidase-like activity of Arabidopsis phytohemoglobin 3 and its role in *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* defense. *Nitric Oxide: Biology and Chemistry*, 68, 150–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.niox.2017.03.004>
- Padilla, P. A., & Roth, M. B. (2001). Oxygen deprivation causes suspended animation in the zebrafish embryo. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 98(13), 7331–7335. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.131213198>
- Pan, Y., Zhang, Y., Zheng, W.-Y., Zhu, M.-Z., Li, H.-Y., Ouyang, W.-J., Wen, Q.-Q., & Zhu, X.-H. (2024). Intermittent Hypobaric Hypoxia Ameliorates Autistic-Like Phenotypes in Mice. *The Journal of Neuroscience: The Official Journal of the Society for Neuroscience*, 44(7), e1665232023. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1665-23.2023>
- Pardee, K. I., Xu, X., Reinking, J., Schuetz, A., Dong, A., Liu, S., Zhang, R., Tiefenbach, J., Lajoie, G., Plotnikov, A. N., Botchkarev, A., Krause, H. M., & Edwards, A. (2009). The structural basis of

- gas-responsive transcription by the human nuclear hormone receptor REV-ERBbeta. *PLoS Biology*, 7(2), e43. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1000043>
- Perrella, M., Bresciani, D., & Rossi-Bernardi, L. (1975). The binding of CO₂ to human hemoglobin. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 250(14), 5413–5418.
- Reed, E. C., Kim, J. D., & Case, A. J. (2025). Non-canonical hemoglobin: An updated review on its ubiquitous expression. *Redox Biology*, 82, 103602. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2025.103602>
- Reeder, B. J. (2023). Insights into the function of cytoglobin. *Biochemical Society Transactions*, 51(5), 1907–1919. <https://doi.org/10.1042/BST20230081>
- Reeder, B. J., Deganutti, G., Ukeri, J., Atanasio, S., Svistunenko, D. A., Ronchetti, C., Mobarec, J. C., Welbourn, E., Asaju, J., Vos, M. H., Wilson, M. T., & Reynolds, C. A. (2024). The circularly permuted globin domain of androglobin exhibits atypical heme stabilization and nitric oxide interaction. *Chemical Science*, 15(18), 6738–6751. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4sc00953c>
- Saha, D., Patgaonkar, M., Shroff, A., Ayyar, K., Bashir, T., & Reddy, K. V. R. (2014). Hemoglobin Expression in Nonerythroid Cells: Novel or Ubiquitous? *International Journal of Inflammation*, 2014, 803237. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/803237>
- Shephard, F., Greville-Heygate, O., Marsh, O., Anderson, S., & Chakrabarti, L. (2014). A mitochondrial location for haemoglobins—Dynamic distribution in ageing and Parkinson’s disease. *Mitochondrion*, 14(100), 64–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mito.2013.12.001>
- Teodoro, R. O., & O’Farrell, P. H. (2003). Nitric oxide-induced suspended animation promotes survival during hypoxia. *The EMBO Journal*, 22(3), 580–587. <https://doi.org/10.1093/emboj/cdg070>
- Ulrich, L. E., Koonin, E. V., & Zhulin, I. B. (2005). One-component systems dominate signal transduction in prokaryotes. *Trends in Microbiology*, 13(2), 52–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2004.12.006>
- Villar, I., Larrainzar, E., Milazzo, L., Pérez-Rontomé, C., Rubio, M. C., Smulevich, G., Martínez, J. I., Wilson, M. T., Reeder, B., Huertas, R., Abbruzzetti, S., Udvardi, M., & Becana, M. (2020). A Plant Gene Encoding One-Heme and Two-Heme Hemoglobins With Extreme Reactivities Toward Diatomic Gases and Nitrite. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 11, 600336. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.600336>
- Vinogradov, S. N., Hoogewijs, D., Bailly, X., Arredondo-Peter, R., Gough, J., Dewilde, S., Moens, L., & Vanfleteren, J. R. (2006). A phylogenomic profile of globins. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 6(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-6-31>
- Wang, R. (2002). Two’s company, three’s a crowd: Can H₂S be the third endogenous gaseous transmitter? *FASEB Journal: Official Publication of the Federation of American Societies for Experimental Biology*, 16(13), 1792–1798. <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.02-0211hyp>
- Wang, S., Huang, Y., Liu, S., Lin, Z., Zhang, Y., & Bao, Y. (2021). Hemoglobins from Scapharca subcrenata (Bivalvia: Arcidae) likely play a bactericidal role through their peroxidase activity. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology. Part B, Biochemistry & Molecular Biology*, 253, 110545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpb.2020.110545>
- Wang, S., Yu, X., Lin, Z., Zhang, S., Xue, L., Xue, Q., & Bao, Y. (2017). Hemoglobins Likely Function as Peroxidase in Blood Clam Tegillarca granosa Hemocytes. *Journal of Immunology Research*, 2017, 7125084. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/7125084>
- Winger, J. A., Derbyshire, E. R., & Marletta, M. A. (2007). Dissociation of nitric oxide from soluble guanylate cyclase and heme-nitric oxide/oxygen binding domain constructs. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 282(2), 897–907. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M606327200>
- Wuichet, K., Cantwell, B. J., & Zhulin, I. B. (2010). Evolution and phyletic distribution of two-component signal transduction systems. *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, 13(2), 219–225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2009.12.011>

Zhu, H., & Riggs, A. F. (1992). Yeast flavohemoglobin is an ancient protein related to globins and a reductase family. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 89(11), 5015–5019. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.89.11.5015>

Heme-based one-component signaling system gasoreceptors

FIGURE 1. Heme-based one-component signaling system gasoreceptors.

In the one-component signaling system, the binding of the gaseous molecule can alter the structure of the protein and in turn alter either the enzymatic activity or the DNA binding transcription factor or repressor activity or the ion channel or anion exchanger activity. e.g. O₂ gasoreceptor *E. coli* DosP phosphodiesterase, *C. elegans* GCY-35 soluble guanylate cyclase; mammalian NO gasoreceptor soluble guanylate cyclase and REV-ERB β .

Hemoglobin: a protogasoreceptor or gasoreceptor

FIGURE 2. Hemoglobin: a protogasoreceptor or gasoreceptor.

Hemoglobin is a potential protogasoreceptor or gasoreceptor for dioxygen (and carbon monoxide). In the proto-component signaling system, the binding of dioxygen prevents hemoglobin's enzyme activity and inhibits its nitric oxide-based signaling role. Lack of dioxygen binding during hypoxia allows hemoglobin to synthesize nitric oxide, a gaseous signaling molecule. In the split-component signaling system, the binding of dioxygen can alter the structure of the hemoglobin and alter the binding and potentially also the activity state of the signal transducer such as BAND3 anion exchanger.